

DETERMINANTS OF DELAYED DIAGNOSIS IN PEDIATRIC ANORECTAL MALFORMATIONS: A SINGLE-CENTER EXPERIENCE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17866294>

Keywords

delayed presentation; anorectal malformations; social factors; pediatric surgery; diagnostic delay
Anorectal Malformations, Causes, Children, Delayed Presentation

Article History

Received: 19 October 2025

Accepted: 24 November 2025

Published: 09 December 2025

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Abstract

Background: Anorectal malformations (ARM) require early diagnosis and timely surgical intervention, yet delayed presentation remains common and may adversely affect surgical management and functional outcomes. This study examined the causes of delayed presentation in children with ARM.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study (December 2021–June 2025) enrolled 86 children with ARM at Liaquat University Hospital, Pakistan. Data from parental interviews using a predesigned proforma were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0.

Results: Of 86 patients (median age 0.10 months; 74.4% males), social factors were the predominant cause of delayed presentation (89.5%, n=77), followed by incorrect treatment advice (43.0%, n=37) and constipation masking the diagnosis (26.7%, n=23).

Conclusions: Social factors are the leading cause of delayed ARM presentation, followed by incorrect medical advice. Targeted community awareness programs and healthcare provider education may improve early diagnosis and timely access to surgical care.

INTRODUCTION

Anorectal malformations (ARMs) comprise a wide spectrum of birth defects ranging from simple, easily treatable malformations to more complex types requiring multiple corrective surgeries and consequently leading to more severe limitations on daily living [1,2]. These malformations are among the most common congenital anomalies dealt with by pediatric surgeons, occurring in approximately 1 of every

2,500 to 5,000 live births. Though there is a slight male preponderance, there is no racial predilection as it is seen across all continents [3,4].

The majority of patients with ARM present immediately after birth. However, a significant number of patients report later during infancy or even late childhood [5]. In principle, most ARMs should be diagnosed during routine

neonatal examination within the first 24 hours of birth. A delay in diagnosis may occur at all levels of the healthcare system but is largely due to inadequate or inexperienced initial examination of the newborn [6]. On occasions, ARMs are missed by the family if the neonate is born at home. Even in developed countries, up to 53% of patients may experience a delay in diagnosis [7,8].

The causes of delayed presentation have been documented as delayed detection, wrong advice to parents, inadequate treatment offered, and social causes [9,10]. If the malformation is missed within the first few hours of birth, the baby is fed and taken home. In such children, massive abdominal distension causes respiratory distress, bacterial translocation leading to sepsis, vomiting, and consequences of aspiration pneumonitis, which worsen morbidity and account for significant mortality [11,12].

Once an ARM is diagnosed, delay in transferring the patient to appropriate care can occur due to clinical instability, shortage of suitable ambulance services, or lack of capacity at referral centers [13]. Delay is associated with morbidity including pre-renal impairment secondary to fluid losses, respiratory distress from abdominal distension or aspiration, intestinal perforation, urinary tract infections, unnecessary colostomy, and mortality [14,15].

A pilot study reported causes of delayed presentation as constipation (12%), wrong treatment advice (27.8%), and social factors (14.2%) [16]. Such delayed presentation affects surgical management and contributes to functional and psychological problems for both children and their parents [17].

The surgical approach to repairing these defects changed dramatically in 1980 with the introduction of the posterior sagittal approach by Peña, which allowed surgeons to view the anatomy of these defects, repair them under direct vision, and learn about the complex anatomic arrangement of the junction of the rectum and genitourinary tract [18,19]. Better imaging techniques and improved knowledge of anatomy and physiology of pelvic structures at birth have refined diagnosis and initial management [20].

The morbidity and mortality associated with anorectal malformations are largely avoidable,

and efforts must be directed to lessen the burden of disease and its associated complications. A timely and accurate diagnosis with quick presentation to hospital may yield fruitful outcomes. Identifying factors associated with delayed presentation may help foster deeper understanding and facilitate policy making. There is a dearth of local literature in this regard, warranting this study to determine current statistics of causes of delayed presentation of children with anorectal malformations in our local setup.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Paediatric Surgery, LUMHS, Jamshoro, Pakistan, from December 2021 to June 2025. Sample size (n=86) was calculated using WHO calculator with 12% constipation frequency, 7% margin of error, and 95% confidence level. Non-probability consecutive sampling was used.

ARM was defined as congenital malformations of rectum and anal canal with absent anal opening with/without urogenital fistula. Delayed presentation was defined as ARM diagnosis or referral occurring >24 hours after birth. Causes included constipation, incorrect medical advice, and social factors (non-affordability, limited healthcare access). All neonates with ARM presenting with delayed presentation were included, while those with cloacal exstrophy, common cloaca, or parental consent refusal were excluded.

All patients were enrolled after obtaining written informed parental consent. Causes of delayed presentation were recorded using a predesigned proforma. Data confidentiality was maintained through coding and password protection.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.0. Shapiro-Wilk test assessed normality. Median with interquartile range was calculated for age and weight (non-normal distribution). Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Stratification by age, gender, weight, and residential status was performed, with Chi-square/Fisher's Exact test applied ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS

A total of 86 patients were included to determine the causes of delayed presentation of children with anorectal malformations. The Shapiro-Wilk test revealed non-normal distribution for both age (P=0.0001) and weight (P=0.0001) (Table 1). Patient age ranged from 0.07 to 120 months with a median of 0.10 months (IQR: 0.06), while weight ranged from 1.90 to 16.0 kg with a median of 2.50 kg (IQR: 0.40). Regarding gender distribution, 64 patients (74.4%) were male and 22 (25.6%) were female.

Among 86 children, 54 (62.8%) were rural residents while 32 (37.2%) were urban residents. Social factors were the most common cause of delayed presentation, noted in 77 children (89.5%), followed by incorrect treatment advice

in 37 children (43.0%) and constipation in 23 children (26.7%) (Figure 1).

Stratification analysis revealed several statistically significant associations between demographic variables and causes of delayed presentation (Tables 2 & 3). Age group showed significant association with constipation (P=0.0001), wrong treatment advice (P=0.050), and social factors (P=0.014). Gender demonstrated significant association with constipation (P=0.0001). Weight was significantly associated with all three causes: constipation (P=0.0001), wrong treatment advice (P=0.009), and social factors (P=0.025). Residential status showed significant association only with social factors (P=0.0001).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Shapiro-Wilk Test (n=86)

Variable	Mean ± SD	P-Value
Age group (months)	2.75 ± 13.75	0.0001
Weight (kg)	2.98 ± 1.90	0.0001

Applied Shapiro-Wilk test

Figure 1: Causes of Delayed Medical Presentations

Table 2: Stratification of Age Group with Causes of Delayed Presentation (n=86)

Causes	Response	Age 0-3 months	Age >3 months	P-Value
Constipation	Yes	17 (19.8%)	6 (7.0%)	0.0001
	No	63 (73.3%)	0 (0.0%)	
Wrong treatment advice	Yes	32 (37.2%)	5 (5.8%)	0.050
	No	54 (62.8%)	23 (26.7%)	

	No	48 (55.8%)	1 (1.2%)	
Social Factor	Yes	74 (86.0%)	3 (3.5%)	0.014
	No	6 (7.0%)	3 (3.5%)	

Applied Chi-Square test

Table 3: Stratification of Gender with Causes of Delayed Presentation (n=86)

Causes	Response	Male	Female	P-Value
Constipation	Yes	9 (10.7%)	13 (15.5%)	0.0001
	No	55 (65.5%)	7 (8.3%)	
Wrong treatment advice	Yes	27 (32.1%)	9 (10.7%)	0.824
	No	37 (44.0%)	11 (13.1%)	
Social Factor	Yes	59 (70.2%)	17 (20.2%)	0.388
	No	5 (6.0%)	3 (3.6%)	

Applied Fisher's Exact test

4. DISCUSSION

The delayed presentation of children with anorectal malformations can be attributed to various factors, including social, cultural, medical, and psychological aspects. Anorectal malformations are congenital abnormalities affecting the development of the anus and rectum, leading to functional and anatomical challenges [21]. Delayed presentation occurs when these conditions are not identified or addressed promptly, often due to factors such as limited healthcare access, lack of awareness, misconceptions, or societal stigmas [22].

Anorectal malformations range in severity from imperforate anal membrane to complete caudal regression [23]. Although the majority of anomalies are detected in the neonatal period, a significant number of patients report at a later age. Delayed management increases surgical and functional complications [24].

All newborn babies should undergo a comprehensive, routine pre-discharge neonatal examination to detail good health, sufficient for discharge, and exclude common structural congenital malformations and abnormalities [25]. The ectopic opening of the rectum is either partially or totally outside the sphincter complex. In males, more complex malformations connect internally to the lower urinary tract, while similar malformations in females result in a fistula within the vulval introitus [26].

Complex ARMs, referred to as 'high' anomalies, require a colostomy as the first in a series of staged procedures for reconstruction. Less

complex malformations with abnormal openings on the perineum, often referred to as 'low' anomalies, are treated with a single, primary reconstruction [27]. All abnormalities of the anorectum cause problems of evacuation, and delayed diagnosis is associated with complications due to effects of constipation or delay and alteration of surgical management [28].

In our study, social factors were found in 77 children (89.5%), making it the most prevalent cause of delayed presentation. This finding is substantially higher than the 14.2% reported in a pilot study [16]. The difference may be attributed to regional variations in healthcare infrastructure, socioeconomic conditions, and accessibility to specialized pediatric surgical services in our setting.

Wrong treatment advice was identified in 43.0% of our patients, which is higher than the 27.8% reported previously [16]. This highlights the need for improved education and training among primary healthcare providers regarding recognition and appropriate referral of patients with anorectal malformations. The finding that a substantial proportion of patients received incorrect initial advice underscores the importance of standardized protocols and guidelines for managing these cases at all levels of healthcare.

Constipation was observed in 26.7% of our patients, compared to 12% in the pilot study [16]. Constipation can mask the presence of anorectal malformations, particularly in cases with perineal fistulas where some degree of

evacuation is possible [29]. Parents and healthcare providers may attribute symptoms to functional constipation rather than recognizing the underlying anatomical abnormality.

The significant association between rural residence and social factors ($P=0.0001$) reflects the challenges faced by populations living in areas with limited access to specialized healthcare facilities. Rural residents often face barriers including distance to healthcare facilities, lack of transportation, financial constraints, and limited awareness about congenital anomalies [30].

The male predominance (74.4%) in our study is consistent with literature reporting a slight male preponderance in anorectal malformations [3]. The significant association between gender and constipation ($P=0.0001$) may relate to differences in the types of malformations between males and females, with certain variants more likely to present with constipation symptoms.

The prognosis of ARM is related to the complexity of the malformation. Some of the most complex malformations are not easily treatable by all practitioners and may be best handled by experts who are more familiar with them [31]. Early diagnosis allows for timely surgical intervention, preventing complications such as intestinal obstruction, sepsis, and electrolyte imbalances [32].

Levitt and Pena emphasized that anorectal malformations represent a spectrum of abnormalities ranging from mild anal anomalies to complex cloacal malformations, with etiology remaining unclear and likely multifactorial [33]. Research suggests a genetic component, with increased risk for siblings of affected patients compared to the general population [34].

The main concerns for surgeons in correcting these anomalies are bowel control, urinary control, and sexual function [35]. With early diagnosis, management of associated anomalies, and efficient meticulous surgical repair, patients have the best chance for good functional outcomes. Fecal and urinary incontinence can occur even with excellent anatomic repair, primarily due to associated problems such as poorly developed sacrum, deficient nerve supply, and spinal cord anomalies [36].

Associated anomalies, particularly genitourinary defects occurring in approximately 50% of patients, necessitate comprehensive evaluation at birth [37]. The VACTERL association (vertebral, anorectal, cardiac, tracheoesophageal, renal, and limb anomalies) must be considered in the workup of these patients [38].

The limitations of this study include its single-center design, relatively small sample size, and the cross-sectional nature which limits causal inference. The reliance on parental recall for determining causes of delay may introduce recall bias. Future multicenter prospective studies with larger sample sizes would provide more robust evidence.

5. CONCLUSION

Social factors were identified as the most common causes of delayed presentation of children with anorectal malformations (89.5%), followed by wrong treatment advice (43.0%) and constipation (26.7%). Rural residence was significantly associated with social factors contributing to delayed presentation. These findings emphasize the need for early recognition and intervention, proper medical guidance through improved healthcare provider education, and addressing significant social determinants of health to ensure timely access to appropriate care for young patients with anorectal malformations. Community awareness programs, strengthening of referral networks, and capacity building at primary healthcare levels are recommended interventions. More well-controlled prospective multicenter trials are needed to validate and expand upon these findings.

Conflict of Interest: None declared.

Funding: This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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